

Adding Content and Language Targets to Web 2.0 Projects

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Abstract

Web 2.0 software can be used to create and store animated movies, multimedia slide shows, and comic strips online. A teacher planning to do web 2.0 projects in the computer classroom has many decisions to make, and much to be aware of when planning lessons. A description of how we used VoiceThread, Pixton and Xtranormal will be covered in this report. This software will be described and discussed in terms of teacher and student perceived advantages and disadvantages. Detailed lesson plans and resources are also presented.

Keywords: Web 2.0, VoiceThread, Pixton, Xtranormal, Reflective Thinking, Multimedia Projects

ウェブ 2.0 ソフトウェアを活用すると、アニメーションを使った映画やマルチメディアのスライドショー、コマ割り漫画などをオンライン上で作成したり、保存することができます。ウェブ 2.0 を授業に取り入れるにあたっては、多くの決定が伴うほか、教員は多くのことを知っておく必要があります。このレポートは、私たちがどのようにボイススレッドやピクストン、エクストラノーマルを使用したかについて記述しています。また、私たちが使用したソフトウェアの説明や、教員及び生徒/学生が感じた長所・短所に関する考察や詳細な授業計画、資料についても記述しています。

キーワード

ウェブ 2.0、ボイススレッド、ピクストン、エクストラノーマル、反省的思考、マルチメディア プロジェクト

In this teaching application report we will briefly discuss web 2.0 per se, and then discuss three online web 2.0 applications used in language classes from both teacher and student perspectives. We will share our lesson plans for VoiceThread, Pixton, and Xtranormal that were used with returnee 3rd year junior high school students, and university 2nd year English major, lower intermediate and intermediate students in Japan. After an introduction to the software, and a discussion of their perceived advantages and disadvantages, we will offer appendices with detailed lesson plans as well as web resources we found to be useful.

Web 2.0 has enabled end user interactions and collaborations with features such as "interactive information sharing, interoperability, user centered design, and collaboration on the World Wide Web" (Kennedy, 2007). Development from web 1.0 to web 2.0 has enabled software to load directly into a computer browser and has resulted in a boom of Internet related teaching activities and websites devoted to educational activities (Mollman, 2009). EFL classroom activities with web 2.0 have included creating personalized web pages to upload and share information and interests; making and uploading digital audio files; amending Wikipedia entries; and using Skype to text chat, telephone, or videoconference anywhere on the World Wide Web. Software applications such as VoiceThread, Pixton, and Xtranormal have been used in classrooms to create and share digital slideshows, animations, and comics (Kaechele, 2009).

VoiceThread, Pixton, and Xtranormal

VoiceThread

VoiceThread is a software tool that allows students to create multimedia slideshows. In our classes the goal was to have students share a life experience such as a vacation abroad, a hobby, or a best friend, with other students. Students initially upload images to their computers. They then loaded images into the VoiceThread software. Images came from their SD cards on their cell phones. Students then created narratives by adding text or voice to the images. Students were encouraged to make thoughtful

comments on each other's VoiceThread pages. The ultimate goal was to encourage students think reflectively.

Pixton

Pixton Comics illustrator allows students to illustrate comic panels by choosing from a fixed set of characters. Students can then change the characters' body positions, clothing, and facial features such as hair and eye color. They can crop the scenes by zooming in on any aspect of the panel. They can create dialogues and develop stories through multiple illustrated panels. Students ultimately convey a message to one another through their panel illustration and storytelling ability. Students' favorite Japanese manga are a rich source of content for discussions about character, storyline, and comic themes. Story telling technique such as choice of word, choice of movement, choice of frame, or choice of scene are other aspects for students to think about and can be introduced through "Making Comics" by Scott McCloud (2006).

Xtranormal

Xtranormal is a text-to-image, animation, movie-making software application¹. While using free Xtranormal software students can select two avatars and place them into preset scenes. Students can then type text for the characters to speak. The students can make the characters interact by choosing facial expressions, gestures, accents, and intonations. They can also add sound and music to affect their scenes. University students studied a brief unit on culture, and then portrayed critical incidents with clear conflicts and conflict resolutions. Junior high students imagined how things would be different in the year 2020 and made animated movies depicting what they perceived the future to be.

Interoperability

Interoperability refers to end users being allowed to make changes to "interact and function with other systems without limitations" (Wikipedia, 2010). Thus, whereas web 1.0 users "were passive receivers of information", Web 2.0 "allows users to change the

¹ All three applications covered in this report are browser loading software. For the purpose of this article we use the terms "software" and "application" interchangeably to describe them.

content of a website" (Wikipedia, 2010). To illustrate, if the teacher has created a slideshow with VoiceThread *on the teacher's computer* to show the students, then the students will be able to comment directly on the teacher's slideshow web pages *with their computers*. In other words, students can be linked to each other through a class website, for example VoiceThread, and share a web page holding all class titles. Then students can embark on a journey to visit any page of any slideshow and leave comments for the slideshow creator, and also make remarks about other students' comments. With proper instruction students can then analyze the quality of their classmates work in terms of perceived strengths and weaknesses.

Advantages and disadvantages of web 2.0 software

In our experience we found that web 2.0 software can be both advantageous and disadvantageous for teachers and students. This section is a discussion of what we found the advantages and disadvantages to be. Advantages will be discussed first, and arranged as advantages concerning online resource, the noticing triggering function, classroom community and reflective thinking, and advantages from student perceptions. Disadvantages will be discussed in terms of teacher burdens, and student perceptions of learning disadvantages.

Advantages of web 2.0

Resources

A major advantage for teachers planning a web 2.0 project is the easily accessible plans found online. There are a number of website featuring plans for web 2.0 projects. These plans comprise instructions, target language goals, assessment criteria, and graphic organizers, etc. Two examples of very good examples of online resource access are *Digitally Speaking VoiceThread* and *Blog of Proximal Development* (Glogowski, 2008). These websites portray the reflective thinking process, and ways of fostering a classroom community with web 2.0 software. Other websites, such as *e-moderation station* cover and archive a gamut of web uses such as podcasts, wikis, blogs, poster making, animated cartoon making, etc. Ways of using VoiceThread to teach classes in English/Language arts, information technology, foreign language, mathematics, professional development, etc. are all archived in the VoiceThread library (VoiceThread

Library, 2010). Similarly, from Pixton's project bank archive you can import projects that have been used in world languages, art & design, business & economics, science, social studies, etc. (Pixton, 2008-2010:1).

Noticing triggering functions

Describing known things with known language was a part of many of our web 2.0 classes. Allowing students to use what was already familiar may have operated as a powerful learning tool. While speaking and writing from their own personal experiences, or while listening to or reading easily comprehensible experiences of others, students likely gained knowledge of gaps in their own English ability. This was because the tasks intrinsically were of a low cognitive load. Working primarily in the realm of the known may have enable students to notice gaps in their understanding of language features they hadn't previously noticed (Nation, 2009). According to Nation, the noticing triggering function is activated when students have low cognitive loads. Furthermore, students tend to try to solve the problems they have encountered once they become aware of them through the noticing triggering function. Strategies employed by students to understand gaps in their knowledge could be as simple as consulting classmates, the dictionary, or the instructor.

Reflective thinking and classroom communities

Sharing web 2.0 files contributed to a sense of classroom community in our classes. Students were able to share their work with one another simply by exchanging files within the web 2.0 mediums. With coaching students were able to make thoughtful comments, and advise one another how to improve their work. As students became aware of how other students perceived their work, they also seemed to take more pride in their own work. Students engaged in giving advice or encouragement, while assessing the overall impact of their own, and classmates' contributions to the learning, seemed to help them understand the importance and maintenance of a classroom community. The concept and importance of a classroom community is explained at *The Web of Proximal Development* website (Glogowski, 2008).

Student perceived advantages

According to students there using web 2.0 software offered several advantages. Students

commented that they appreciated the opportunities to engage their creativity, and to use their latent English knowledge to produce new language constructions. Students often commented on the value of making their own original sentences, using conversational phrases, and creating original stories. Students appreciated the storage and retrieval functions that the web 2.0 software provided. They commented on the utility of replaying or repeated viewings of classmates work. Students said software that enabled repeated listening to words or phrases was helpful in comprehending difficult content. Students also said that having opportunities to recycle new language in concurrent web projects was useful.

Disadvantages of web 2.0

Teacher burdens

There are costs that need to be weighed against benefits when doing a web 2.0 project. Setting up web 2.0 projects can be burdensome for teachers inexperienced with software applications. Once a teacher understands how to use the software, they must also find or prepare web 2.0 examples for the students. Teachers must then consider the ways of using the software to teach content and language features. Teachers must plan additional interactive tasks that support student comprehension and use of language targets. Teachers must also prepare assessment criteria, and endeavor to direct students towards these criteria throughout all stages of a web 2.0 project.

Student perceived disadvantages

There were student perceived disadvantages to web 2.0 projects. The time to complete web 2.0 projects may require much of the class time, as many students do not have computers at home. Thus, the production of web 2.0 projects can require many class periods. Students might not comprehend the benefits of doing web 2.0 software projects when the improvements to their language ability happen subtly over time. Students may also want class time for direct face-to-face interaction with classmates, as this seems to be something they value.

Placating students' needs for face-to-face interactions will further slow down the production time for projects. It may also be critical to allow time for the students to think reflectively to uncover their language progress in a web 2.0 learning environment.

Conclusion

Web 2.0 software is readily accessible and provides a medium for students to produce target language output, and to be exposed to many inputs. It also seems to be a way to allow students to channel their creativity. Thus, the software may be intrinsically interesting to use. However, teachers considering implementing web 2.0 software in their language classrooms should consider the classroom advantages and disadvantages of the software. Advantages of web 2.0 software include the number of readily accessible web 2.0 resources, a likely activation of a students noticing triggering function, a heightened sense of classroom community via the ease of sharing student work, group reflective thinking, and other student perceived advantages such as using language creatively. Disadvantages of web 2.0 were teacher preparation burdens, the amount of time given over to production of web 2.0 files, and student desires for more face-to-face time. Students may not immediately understand the value of web 2.0 projects in relation to their English development, as their improvements are subtle, and students may be required to think reflectively about what they have learnt once a project is finished to uncover their own progress.

In our experiences the advantages outweighed the disadvantages in engaging students, unlocking their creativity and facilitating a community that shared, discussed and reflected on their learning.

Bio data

Michael Riffle is currently working for Ryukoku University. His interests include professional development, developing curriculum for Computer Aided Language Learning, Extensive Reading.

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Appendix

In the following three appendices we list how VoiceThread, Pixton, and Xtranormal can be used in the classroom, what the technical requirements are, example projects, with teacher preparation and tasks. Finally, there is a resource list for each application.

Appendix 1: Using VoiceThread in the classroom

It is a good idea for an entire class to use one account for VoiceThread. Each class member can create a slideshow with text or voiced comments. Other class members can then navigate pages, and leave comments, while receiving comments on their own VoiceThread pages.

Table 2. Requirements for using VoiceThread (VoiceThread FAQ, 2010)

Computers	Normal internet connection access and speed is sufficient but a minimum of flash player 7.0 is required to use the VoiceThread software.
Student e-mail	Not required: However, it is important to sign up as an educator. Free educator accounts are sufficient for the project described. Go the 'about' link at the bottom of the VoiceThread homepage. Click on K-12 under solutions/Purchase Options/Single K-12 Educator/and Apply (under VT Educator) to get started. Optionally, if you have a budget, a one-year class subscription costs \$60 and will have a domain to manage 100 students.
Tech difficulty	It is easy to set up VoiceThread projects. The microphones can be tricky and the software sometimes freezes. These problems can be overcome with some easy fixes, such as turning of the main projector. Experiment with the microphone/speaker settings and/or check with your institution's computer support department.
Teacher prep	A minimum of 3-5 hours.

Ways of using VoiceThread in classroom projects:

There are many different ways to do various VoiceThread projects. A good idea when getting started is to go to the VoiceThread resources link at the end of the VoiceThread appendix to research the various ways VoiceThread has been used by educators.

Student tasks in VoiceThread projects

It is common for a teacher to ask students to prepare a report on an area of self-interest such as a memorable experience, a routine such as a club activity, or a topic of interest. Students are also tasked with gathering digital images from their digital cameras, their Facebook or Mixi accounts, or to gather images from the Internet. Students are then asked to transfer their images into a folder created on their computers. Once images are on their computers they must upload the images into a VoiceThread and begin a commenting process.

Teacher preparation

1. Create an email account.
2. Set up you own Educator's account (up to 50 VoiceThreads free).
3. Download and install the latest flash player if needed (a minimum of flash player 7.0).
4. Learn to set up the microphone, learn the controls, learn how to manage glitches, freezes, bad microphones, etc.
5. Develop a context, themes, and teaching plans.
6. Create a folder for images that you upload or download onto your computer.
7. Create a VoiceThread by uploading your pictures onto the web page, write the text to accompany your slide show, and finally add this text or voiced text to your VoiceThread.

Student tasks (Digitally Speaking VoiceThread, 2009)

1. Small group discussions are used to derive themes such as a desired area of inquiry, an interesting routine activity, an exciting life-changing experience such as a home stay abroad.
2. Develop an experiential narrative or area of interest theme.

3. Gather images from digital cameras or the Internet and put these into an 'Image Folder' on their desktops.
4. Type and proof all text written to support the pictures in MS Word or equivalent.
5. Upload images into the VoiceThread software, add a title to each image and give the whole VoiceThread a title and description.
6. Add text and/or voice to the VoiceThread images.
7. Have students view class mates' VoiceThreads.
8. Use 'Sentence Starter' target language when commenting on classmates' VoiceThreads (see resources).
9. Use 'agreeing and disagreeing' target language when agreeing or disagreeing with others (see resources).
10. Use a set of criteria to evaluate the utility of classmates' comments on a range from 'not useful' to 'inspiring' or 'thought provoking'.
11. Use critical thinking when applying these criteria to 'score' classmates' comments.

Desired outcomes for our students

Our learning outcome and experiences were developed in accordance with the eVALUate survey that was developed for quality control assurance at Curtin University. The construct learning outcomes are used to refer to what students are expected to know, understand, or be able to do. Learning experiences refer to what helped the students achieve the learning outcomes. These may refer to face-to-face lectures, tutorials, laboratories, clinical practicums, etc. (Oliver & Tucker & Gupta & Yeo, 2008). These terms will be used throughout the appendix to describe our desired outcome and experiences.

- To be able to use the VoiceThread online software to make a picture essay with text and voice
- To be able to use the various kinds of target language for making comments
- To be able to evaluate comments as good or bad according to a set of criteria
- To be able to have an intelligent digital discussion

Learning Experiences for our students

- Downloading pictures

- Uploading pictures
- Making a VoiceThread
- Making text comments
- Making microphone comments
- Making comments about comments
- Evaluating comments

VoiceThread resources

Our Web 2.0 site with links and extra information

<<https://sites.google.com/site/web20presentation2010/>>.

VoiceThread Wiki: Join the conversation

<<https://jointheconversation.wikispaces.com/file/view/VThandout.pdf>>.

VoiceThread examples in education

<slideshare.net/suziea/Voicethread-examples-in-education-presentation?from=share_email>.

VoiceThread library

<ed.VoiceThread.com/library/>.

Digitally Speaking (commenting etc)

<digitallyspeaking.pbworks.com/Voicethread>.

Appendix 2: Using Pixton in the classroom

Pixton is an online comic creator that was started in 2008. It is a great way to capture students' attention, use their imagination and use as a pathway to literacy (Baird, 2009).

Membership

You can either join Pixton for Fun (public and free), Pixton for Schools (about US \$1/per month/student) or Pixton for Business. The Pixton for Schools account gives you access to a large range of projects and tools for managing your class but you can do projects having students use individual accounts (Pixton, 2008-2010:1).

Table 3. Requirements for using Pixton:

Computers	Normal internet connection access and speed is sufficient but a minimum of flash player 7.0 is required to use the Pixton software.
Student e-mail	On an educators account students don't need their own email account but they do for the normal free version.
Tech difficulty	It is completely "click and drag" with good "How to videos". Projects can be imported from the project bank (for School accounts only) and edited for your circumstance and goals.
Teacher prep	A minimum of 2-4 hours, more if you create elaborate comics.
Cost	For a Pixton for Schools account, you pay per student, per month. 30 students cost 2,657 yen per month, less for longer periods. You can try an account with 30 students for 14 days free of charge (Pixton 2008-2010:2).

The educator account has help with setting up student list and projects but free accounts can still be used. Here are some recommended steps for doing your own student project.

Teacher preparation

- 1) Set up your own free account (you can upgrade to an educator account later if you wish).
- 2) Watch all "How to videos".
- 3) Do a few comics, start with "Quickies".
- 4) Browse for other tutorial comics and inspirational material.
- 5) Decide on theme/topic/goal for student project.

Optional

- 1) Show students some normal comics to set the scene.
- 2) Teach about choice of word, choice of movement, choice of frame, choice of scene etc (McCloud, 2006).

Student tasks

1) Create an account.

Can be part of teacher's educator account or own free account.

2) Create an avatar/Picture.

This helps in learn in the controls in a structured setting and personalizes their work.

3) Remix a set comic or do a Quickie comic.

Specific tasks can be set for what the students should do. It is easier to set up with an educator account but can be done without it. Help students with control problems and ask quicker students to help their friends.

Once all students have created/remixed one comic, teach the students how to comment on each other's comics. The comments are an essential part of learning from each other and can bring in more language learning in the project. Set a criterion for what and how you want them to comment (Digitally Speaking VoiceThread, 2009).

4) Have students email 3-5 class mates + the teacher their comic.

On an educators account there are other options for sharing the comics within the class and settings for how the commenting can be done but emailing works well.

5) Comment on about 3-5 classmates comics.

The initial comments will be mostly unhelpful ones like "I really liked your comic", "LOL".

6) Evaluate the comments received; which ones were most helpful to you?

By evaluating the comments they received from their classmates they can learn about how to improve their own commenting for the next round.

7) Do a "Super Long Comic" on a set theme/topic.

It helps the students get started and you evaluating them if you have a theme for the longer comic. It can be topic- or task-based.

8) Share your comic and comment on about 3-5 classmates' comics.

Emphasize that the comments should be more specific, highlighting good parts and parts that could be improved, or any criteria you set for you class.

9) Respond to the comments received and edit your comic if necessary.

Before the final vote/evaluation give students a chance to edit spelling mistakes and/or comprehension problems.

10) Vote on the comics, for example "Most creative", "Best looking", "Funniest", "Best dialog".

Students want to see all their friends' comics so either print them (requires credits or,

for example, ‘screen shots’ that are then edited for size and put together), email to all or display on the screens and do a walk around in the classroom.

Desired skills/outcomes for our students

- To be able to create a Pixton account
- To know how to create and edit Pixton comics
- To know how to publish Pixton comics
- To send comics to classmates, friends, and teacher for assessment or comments
- To be able to express humor or seriousness within a fixed 3-panel comic and free-sized comic
- To develop your creativity for characters, themes, narratives, storytelling, and dialogues etc.
- To use: choice of word, choice of movement, choice of frame, choice of scene, etc. to create feeling within your comics
- To be able comment on classmates’ comics
- To be able to evaluate comments as helpful

Student examples: Pixton

Disappointing Valentine by Fuyumi

<pixton.com/from/comic/swtgxlj9>.

HW by Yuta

<pixton.com/from/comic/v6o93ux7>.

Time slip by Momoka

<pixton.com/from/comic/qtmy6g8p>.

Sunset in the fish world by Tsuyoushi

<pixton.com/comic/7i9wc4k1>.

Merry Christmas by Yuko

<pixton.com/from/comic/vg1tslek>.

The traveling umbrella by Aya

<pixton.com/jp/from/comic/i3o1kcwo>.

Lonely Xmas by Aya

<pixton.com/jp/comic/1k9yk4m6>.

The boy & the giant man by Ryousuke

<pixton.com/from/comic/1j7h1r2l>.

Kumi Zero by Mike (teacher)

<pixton.com/from/comic/6ve4t4hx>.

First day with Pixton by Bjorn (teacher)

<pixton.com/uk/comic/h1r2arno>.

Appendix 3: Using Xtranormal in the classroom

Xtranormal is an online movie creator that converts text to movies. It can be run online (recommended) or in a down-loadable version. Currently it is in beta format. The free version is limited to 1 or 2 actors and fewer backgrounds but, “Showpacks” can be purchased and premium accounts are forthcoming (Jorgensen).

Table 3. Requirements for using Xtranormal:

Computers	Fast internet access and computer speed is necessary as well as a minimum of flash player 7.0 to use the Xtranormal software. Please check that your school server supports updating several videos simultaneously. If not, don't attempt this project with larger classes. Having students work in pairs can help the situation.
Student e-mail	Students need their own email account.
Tech difficulty	It is very simple to use with simple typing or click and drag. There are very good “How to” slides shows available on-line.
Teacher prep	A minimum of 1-2 hours, more if you created elaborate videos.
Age	Users need to be at least 13 years of age (Xtranormal 2006-2010:1).

Why use Xtranormal in EFL teaching?

1. Motivation

Great for motivation. Students of various ages get excited by the prospect of actually producing something they could show or send to family and friends.

2. Flexible

Xtranormal can be incorporated in any part of your lesson plan. It can be used with individual students or with groups.

3. Grammar & spelling

Good review of spelling, sentence construction, question word order, reported speech and reported questions, natural conversational language, i.e., phrasal verbs and idioms, turn taking, dialogue development, etc.

4. Functional language

Practice functional language for presentations, testimonials, giving the news, giving a promotional plug for products or services (1 actor).

Introductions, interviews, meetings, hosting a talk show, a sitcom (2 actors).

5. Body language

Helps students become aware of the role body language and sounds play in our conversations. The students need to choose appropriate ambient noise, background music, expressions for their actors and camera movements or angles to match the dialogue (O'Neill, 2010).

Teacher preparation

1) Watch two very good presentations about Xtranormal.

How to use Xtranormal (the basics)

<slideshare.net/digitalmaverick/how-to-use-xtranormal>.

A Tutorial for Xtranormal, (very detailed)

<slideshare.net/Andreatej/xtranormal-tutorial>.

2) Set up your own free account.

3) Do a test video or remix an existing video.

4) Browse for other tutorial videos and inspirational material.

5) Decide on theme/topic/goal for student project.

Student tasks

1) Set the theme/topic for the project.

2) Explain limitations in backgrounds, number of actors and props (unless using purchased show-packs).

3) Create a dialog/monolog in a word document (in pairs, if possible).

4) Create an account.

5) Enter text, play and edit for mispronunciations.

6) Add camera angles, voice, music, body moments, facial expressions, etc.

7) Share with classmates and comment.

- 8) Respond to comments and edit.
- 9) Vote on the movie, for example like your own Oscar awards.

Desired skills/outcomes for our students

- To be able to create a Xtranormal account
- To know how to create Xtranormal video
- To know how to add facial expressions, gestures, accents, and intonations
- To know how to add music and sounds to the scenes
- To be able to portray the studied theme in the video
- To develop your creativity for themes, narratives, storytelling, and dialogues etc.
- To know how to publish Xtranormal video
- To be able to send video to classmates, friends, and teacher for assessment or comments
- To be able comment on classmates' videos
- To be able to evaluate comments as helpful

Xtranormal resources

Our Web 2.0 site with links and extra information

[<https://sites.google.com/site/web20presentation2010/>](https://sites.google.com/site/web20presentation2010/).

How to use Xtranormal (the basics)

[<slideshare.net/digitalmaverick/how-to-use-xtranormal>](http://slideshare.net/digitalmaverick/how-to-use-xtranormal).

A step-by-step guide to how to use Xtranormal (very detailed)

[<slideshare.net/Andreatej/xtranormal-tutorial>](http://slideshare.net/Andreatej/xtranormal-tutorial).

Testimonial of a Language Teacher. It's not just for English learners.

[<boxoftricks.net/?p=1381>](http://boxoftricks.net/?p=1381).

Tips for making the sound better and what project to use Xtranormal for

[<isteconnects.org/2010/01/04/it's-xtranormal-to-blabberize-goanimate-part-3/>](http://isteconnects.org/2010/01/04/it's-xtranormal-to-blabberize-goanimate-part-3/).

Student examples: Xtranormal

Welcome to Manhattan by Miyabi & Rio

[<xtranormal.com/watch/6141509/>](http://xtranormal.com/watch/6141509/).

Life in 2020 by Miwa & Rina

[<xtranormal.com/watch/6141413/>](http://xtranormal.com/watch/6141413/).

2020 Global Warming by Yui & Sayuri

<xtranormal.com/watch/6141367/>.

The Hamburger by Kengo & Tatsuya

<xtranormal.com/watch/6141513/>.

Windows I ® Professional – copyright Windows Inc 2020 by Yamato & Yuta

<xtranormal.com/watch/6141347/>.

Cars in 2020 by Natsuki, Yu & Ken

<xtranormal.com/watch/6141389/>.

2020 by Nozomi & Yurika

<xtranormal.com/watch/6179665/>.

Evolution of Science at 2020 by Utako & Yurina

<xtranormal.com/watch/6141387/>.

Monday Haircut Blues by Yoshie

<xtranormal.com/watch/6130453/>.

In the movies (remixed by Bjorn (teacher))

<xtranormal.com/watch/6621321/>.